

THE ROLE OF THE “MEHRLI MAKTAB” IN CREATING AN EDUCATIONAL AND NURTURING ENVIRONMENT FOR CHILDREN UNDERGOING TREATMENT IN HOSPITALS

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Abstract. *This article describes the positive impact of "Mehrlı Maktab" created at the Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Pediatric Oncology, Hematology and Immunology, on the health and mental state of children. After the start of "Mehrlı Maktab," the positive impact on the emotional state and health of children has increased significantly. This article highlights the concept of hospital education, international and domestic studies conducted in the hospital direction, as well as methodological approaches. A brief description of the differences between hospital education and traditional schools and preschool institutions is given.*

Keywords: *inclusive education, upbringing, hospital education, illness, psychological support, fear, emotional state, cognitive abilities.*

Introduction

In recent years, increasing attention has been paid to the fact that education is an important factor in the intellectual and social development of an individual and should serve to create opportunities for continuous learning for each child. However, at the Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Children's Oncology, Hematology and Immunology, there was no opportunity for continuous learning for children undergoing long-term treatment. That is why the "Mehrlı Maktab" was created for children undergoing long-term treatment [1,2]. The "Mehrlı Maktab" not only provides children with high-quality and continuous education and continues the learning process, but also makes a significant contribution to their socio-psychological adaptation.

From this perspective, it becomes evident that hospital education serves to create an educational and upbringing environment in the hospital, which helps to increase children's interest in life and strengthen their self-confidence [1]. Therefore, as important as it is for society to provide education to children at school, it is equally important to provide continuous education in hospitals for children in need of long-term treatment.

While children acquire the knowledge and skills they need in a traditional school environment, hospital education also helps children and their parents improve their psychological state. After children learn about a serious and long-term illness, their daily lives often experience changes such as fear, depression[2], loss of interest in life and the future, and even a sense of hopelessness.

The medications prescribed to the patient (chemotherapy, injections, various surgeries) affect the mental state of each child differently. In some cases, the child begins to withdraw from the outside world, there are cases of refusal to communicate with peers and relatives. Hospital education plays an important role in the child's recovery from this difficult situation.

Review of relevant literature

It is widely recognized that hospital education has been developing in world practice for many years. In particular, this direction is supported by the state in the USA, Great Britain, Germany, France and Russia. Scientific research and practical experience of hospital education have been widely studied in different countries, and international organizations have also conducted a number of studies in this area. In particular, studies conducted by UNESCO and UNICEF examine in detail the place of hospital education in the inclusive education system and its impact on child development. According to their research, specially adapted educational programs for children undergoing long-term treatment in hospitals have a positive effect on maintaining their academic performance and readaptation to life in society. In recent years, special attention has been paid to the organization of a continuous educational process for children undergoing long-term treatment.

A growing body of research indicates that in Uzbekistan, inpatient education is one of the new developing areas, and the "Mehrli Maktab" project is one of the first practical experiences in creating this system. A number of regulatory documents on the organization of the educational process in hospitals have been developed jointly with the Ministry of Public Education and the Ministry of Health.

International and domestic experience in inpatient education shows that this system not only helps ensure the continuous educational process of children, but also plays a significant role in improving their psychological state, social adaptation and integration into society.

Table 1

The concept of inpatient education

Inpatient education is a specially organized form of education for children in need of long-term treatment, the main purpose of which is to provide the child with psychological and pedagogical support and ensure the continuous continuation of the educational process.

№	Author	Definitions
1	Giuseppina Caggiano	Hospital education is a means of guaranteeing the right to education for children and adolescents with disabilities or chronic illnesses that require long-term hospital stays.
2	Der-Fang Chen	Hospital education is a service that creates a learning environment tailored to the unique needs of sick children and offers formal education programs that meet standards.
3	Lucia Ilaria Giulia Brunetti	The Hospital School is a tool that can guarantee the right to education for children and adolescents with chronic disorders and/or illnesses that require frequent treatment and long hospital stays.
4	Eleanor Tweedie Susie Pace	Hospital school - gives students the opportunity to feel free and understand themselves in a free environment. Because children and adolescents who are treated in the hospital are members of our school. The duration of treatment can be short or long-term, so we know and understand the students well. Our main goal is to help these and other children not to lag behind in the school program and educational skills.

5	Sharikov S.V.	Hospital education is a unique educational environment for children with long-term illness, created in the conditions of inpatient medical facilities.
6	Dr. Cathleen Kuo	Medical school is not just a learning process of textbooks and exams. During my studies, I formed strong friendships with my classmates, who have become my close family today. Together, we overcame all the difficulties and successes that I encountered on the path to medical education. Medical school taught me important human qualities such as cooperation, compassion, and determination. These values continue to guide me in my medical career today. In addition, medical school provided me with the opportunity to conduct practical training in my chosen specialty, participate in advanced scientific research, and receive mentorship from world-renowned professors in their fields.
7	Ivan Yuryevich Doluev	The main task of the hospital schools operating under the hospital is to support children, the specific aspects of the work of the hospital pedagogue-tutor reveal
8	Department of Health & Social Care	Hospital education is a special school organized within a hospital, where children's participation in educational activities is carried out based on the decision of doctors.

Source: prepared by the author.

Research methodology

The following methods were used in this study:

- The efficiency of "Mehrlı maktab" was studied through the experimental method;
- Opinions of parents, doctors and students were analyzed using questionnaires;
- The impact of the project was assessed based on statistical data;
- Pedagogical and psychological approaches were explored through empirical research.

Analysis and results

In the article, the role of "Mehrlı Maktab" teachers (pedagogue, psychologist, speech therapist, social science teacher, educator, etc.) opened in the Scientific and Applied Medical Center of Children's Oncology, Hematology and Immunology is important in ensuring the continuity of the educational process of children and in creating an educational environment in the hospital.

While the main goal of traditional schools and preschools is to educate and nurture children, in the "Mehrlı Maktab" teachers implement educational processes by conducting lessons and activities taking into account the child's time, health, and wishes[3] and by providing spiritual support. If a child feels unwell during the lesson (weakness, nausea, pain, etc.), the activities are temporarily suspended.

It is natural for preschool and school-age children undergoing treatment for health problems to undergo difficult therapies during the treatment. Due to the long-term treatments, the child is forced to spend most of his time in his room. The duration of these treatments and the pain during the treatment process have an impact on the emotional and mental state and cognitive

abilities of some of them. In some cases, changes in the child's attention or concentration are observed.

The results of the analysis show that the "Mehrlı Maktab" state educational institution has the following positive results for children treated in the hospital:

- Children's learning means that they are not falling behind, which facilitates their return to society;
- Provides psychological support and helps maintain mental health;
- Children can continue the process of personal development;
- Despite long-term treatment, social ties are not interrupted;
- Development of special programs by pedagogues allows meeting the individual needs of children.

Conclusions and suggestions

There is a general consensus among scholars that hospital education organized for children in long-term treatment helps to increase their ability to fight the disease, regardless of their health problems. A consistent schedule is important for preschool and school-aged children who require long-term treatment. Hospital education organized in a hospital leads to positive changes in the child's usual lifestyle.

The use of integrations plays an important role in the process of educating preschool and school-age children with pediatric hematology and oncology.

In recent years, attention has been growing to the organization of the educational process in a hospital. This hospital education helps to prevent gaps in the education of preschool and school-age children, (2,4) and increase their self-confidence.

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